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Observations of Mineral Dust Using Novel Remote Sensing and UAV Technologies

PHD DEFENSE

Alkistis Papetta

19TH JANUARY 2026

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Chapter I

Research Background & Motivation

Observations of Mineral Dust Using Novel Remote Sensing
and UAV Technologies

Research Background & Motivation

"Scream", Edvard Munch

"Sunset", Joseph M. W. Turner

"Sunrise", Claude Monet

"Sunrise", Claude Monet

Research Background & Motivation

1883 Krakatoa eruption (Indonesia)

"The sun was setting. The sky suddenly turned blood red... I sensed a scream passing through nature."

1831 eruption of Babuyan (Philippines)

Pollution (coal burning ships and factories) in Le Havre port city

“**Atmospheric aerosols** are solid or liquid particles suspended in the air with diameters from roughly $0.001\ \mu\text{m}$ up to at least several tens of micrometres (including super-coarse and giant particles), and can have different shapes, chemical compositions and hygroscopic and optical properties (Seinfeld et al. 2006).”

Atmospheric Aerosols:

- Affect human health (C. Arden Pope III et al. 2002).

① Source: Garieiro and Garieiro, (2013).

Atmospheric Aerosols:

- Affect human health (C. Arden Pope III et al. 2002).
- Affect everyday life (e.g. reduced visibility, disruption of transportation).

«Πνίγηκε» στη σκόνη η Κύπρος – Η πόλη που βρίσκεται στο «κόκκινο»

22.05.2023 15:41 Κύπρος
SigmaLive

Cyprus is 'drowning' in dust. Cities exceeding allowed

PM10 concentrations

↑Fig. View of Pentadaktylos taken from NTL roof on a dust-free (top) and dusty (bottom) day

←Fig. News article for dust storm during 2023.

Source:
SigmaLive

Atmospheric Aerosols:

- Affect human health (C. Arden Pope III et al. 2002).
- Affect everyday life (e.g. reduced visibility, disruption of transportation).
- **Affect Earth's radiation budget and the global climate.**

Largest uncertainty in the radiative forcing of earth's energy balance (IPCC 2001, IPCC 2007, IPCC 2015, IPCC 2021).

Change in effective radiative forcing (ERF) from 1750 to 2019 (Source: IPCC 2021)

Mineral dust:

Mineral dust:

- The most abundant natural aerosol by mass (2000-3000 Tg/year).

Mineral dust:

- The most abundant natural aerosol by mass (2000-3000 Tg/year).
- Can travel up to several thousands of km away from the source (supplies oceans and Amazon forest with nutrients).

A Massive Cloud of Saharan Dust Is About to Hit The United States

ENVIRONMENT 04 June 2025 By JESS COCKERILL

Graphic of Saharan dust crossing the ocean in 2020. (Copernicus Sentinel/ESA/CC BY-SA 3.0 IGO)

Mineral dust:

- The most abundant natural aerosol by mass (2000-3000 Tg/year).
- Can travel up to several thousands of km away from the source (supplies oceans and Amazon forest with nutrients).
- Wide range of sizes, shapes, and composition.

Mineral dust:

- The most abundant natural aerosol by mass (2000-3000 Tg/year).
- Can travel up to several thousands of km away from the source (supplies oceans and Amazon forest with nutrients).
- Strong dependence on size, shape, and composition.
- Dust observed through various tech tools (e.g. Satellite and ground-based lidars, airborne observations, and sun photometers).

Chapter II

Research Gaps

Observations of Mineral Dust Using Novel Remote Sensing
and UAV Technologies

Observational gaps:

- Limited information on vertical distribution of aerosols (e.g. in climate-sensitive regions like EMME).
- Column-integrated observations dominate (e.g. AOD).

Aerosol emission sources and observations around the EMME and Mediterranean regions.

Volume size distributions during previous airborne campaigns in the Eastern Atlantic (Source: Ryder et al. 2019)

Methodological and Technical gaps:

- Uncertainties in lidar depolarization characterization (affecting dust identification).
- Uncertainties in linking optical and mass-based dust metrics.
- Super-coarse and giant particles are often neglected (by models and observations), leading to an underestimation of dust abundance.

Observational gaps:

- Limited information on vertical distribution of aerosols (e.g. in climate-sensitive regions like EMME).
- Column-integrated observations dominate (e.g. AOD).

Modelling and validation gaps:

- Lack of height-resolved aerosol observations for model validation.
- Understanding dust composition, origin, and mixing.

Methodological and Technical gaps:

- Uncertainties in lidar depolarization characterization (affecting dust identification).
- Uncertainties in linking optical and mass-based dust metrics.
- Super-coarse and giant particles are often neglected (by models and observations), leading to an underestimation of dust abundance.

Chapter III

Research Questions

Observations of Mineral Dust Using Novel Remote Sensing
and UAV Technologies

Q1

How can we ensure that lidar systems accurately distinguish mineral dust from other aerosol types?

Q2

How accurate are remote sensing observations of the dust particle size-distribution?

Q3

How are the optical and gravimetric quantifications of dust related?

Q4

Can the measured optical properties of dust reveal its origin and its mixing state with other aerosols during transport?

Chapter IV

Methods and Results

Observations of Mineral Dust Using Novel Remote Sensing
and UAV Technologies

Q1

Lidar depolarization is key for separating dust and non-dust particles (Nicolae et al. 2018, Illingworth et al. 2015)

High accuracy needed for correct separation (Freudenthaler 2009, 2016)

Q1

Lidar depolarization is key for separating dust and non-dust particles (Nicolae et al. 2018, Illingworth et al. 2015)

High accuracy needed for correct separation (Freudenthaler 2009, 2016)

- LiDAR polarization parameters lead to uncertainties (e.g., Cross-talk in the receivers)

Schematic of a dual polarization lidar setup.

Lidar depolarization characterization using a reference system

- Uses observations in the free troposphere from a reference well-characterized lidar situated nearby.
- Evaluate lidar's gain ratio K^* and cross-talk g , e (a priori knowledge not required).
- Can be applied retrospectively.
- Three parameter depolarization characterization:

$$\delta^* = K^* \frac{\delta + g}{1 + e\delta}$$

Schematic of lidar depolarization characterization using a reference system method.

Q1

Lidar depolarization characterization using a reference system

- 1 Compare volume depolarization profiles from the two lidars.
- 2 Identify at least two dust layers and the molecular layer.
- 3 Retrieve:

- Gain ratio K^*
- cross-talks g & e

$$\delta^* = K^* \frac{\delta + g}{1 + e\delta}$$

Schematic of lidar depolarization characterization using a reference system method.

Q1

Lidar depolarization characterization using a reference system

CIMEL CE376 (tested)

- Unknown cross-talk and gain ratio
- Elastic backscatter lidar (808 and 532 nm)
- Depolarization at 532 nm
- Operated by Cyl, in Nicosia

PollyXT (our reference)

- **Better-characterized lidar following standard calibration procedures**
- Multiwavelength Raman lidar
- Depolarization at 532 and 355 nm.
- Operated by ERATOSTHENESCoE, in Limassol

Lidar depolarization characterization using a reference system

- K^*, g, e calculated for each individual case.
- The derived depolarization parameters are applied to longer periods.

Derived polarization parameters for different profiles.

Comparison of the corrected and non-corrected VDR profiles of CIMEL CE376 using PollyXT as a reference.

Lidar depolarization characterization using a reference system

Comparison of the corrected and non-corrected VDR profiles of CIMEL CE376 using PollyXT as a reference.

Outcomes

- New, observation-based depolarization characterization.
- Applicable retrospectively, enabling use of existing campaign data.
- Compatible with diverse lidar configurations.
- Extending lidar observations with more well characterised lidars.
- **Publication with 4 citations in peer-reviewed papers**

Atmos. Meas. Tech., 17, 1721–1738, 2024
<https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-17-1721-2024>
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Atmospheric
Measurement
Techniques

Lidar depolarization characterization using a reference system

Alkistis Papetta¹, Franco Marengo¹, Maria Kezoudi¹, Rodanthi-Elisavet Mamouri^{2,3}, Argyro Nisantzi^{2,3}, Holger Baars⁴, Ioana Elisabeta Popovici^{5,6}, Philippe Goloub⁶, Stéphane Victori⁵, and Jean Sciare¹

Dust observations

Q1

Q2

Q3

Q4

Map of the average aerosol optical depth measured by SLSTR-A during 2021

Dust observations

Map of the average aerosol optical depth measured by SLSTR-A during 2021

Dust observations

Map of the average aerosol optical depth measured by SLSTR-A during 2021

Dust observations

Dust observations

- Compared observations from two campaigns

Fall Campaign, October-
November 2021, Cyprus

ASKOS, June 2022, Cabo
Verde

Dust observations

- Compared observations from two campaigns

The EMME Region:

- At the Crossroads of Dust and Pollution
- Limited upper air observations of dust size distributions and conversion parameters

Dust observations

- Compared observations from two campaigns

Dust observations

- Compared observations from two campaigns

Dust observations

- Compared observations from two campaigns

Dust particle size distribution

Fig. AERONET vs UAV-based OPC column averaged volume size distributions during the two campaigns.

MIXED DUST CASE

- Good agreement.

PURE DUST- NEAR TO THE SOURCE

- Disagreement in the coarse mode.
- Indication of super-coarse particles existence.

*AERONET upper size limit 15 μm

Dust particle size distribution

- The existence of super-coarse and giant particles have been reported before (Weinzierl et al. 2009, Ryder et al. 2015, van der Does et al. 2018 etc.)
- **One of the first studies reporting co-located observations of super-coarse dust particles with AERONET**

Calculate conversion parameter

Calculate conversion parameter

Using sunphotometry

$$\zeta = \frac{V}{\alpha} = \frac{4}{3} \frac{r_{\text{eff},s}}{\overline{q_{\text{ext},s}}}$$

V : volume concentration
 α : extinction coefficient
 $r_{\text{eff},s}$: effective radius
 $\overline{q_{\text{ext},s}}$: extinction efficiency

Calculate conversion parameter

Using sunphotometry

ADVANTAGES

- Global coverage.
- Continious datasets.

DISADVANTAGES

- Column-averaged measurements.
- Limited size distribution range (<15 μ m).

Calculate conversion parameter

Combining UAV-based and ground based lidar observations.

$$\zeta = \frac{V}{\alpha}$$

Calculate conversion parameter

Combining UAV-based and ground based lidar observations.

$$\zeta = \frac{V}{\alpha}$$

Calculate conversion parameter

Combining UAV-based and ground based lidar observations.

$$\zeta = \frac{V}{\alpha}$$

ADVANTAGES

- Vertically resolved extinction and volume concentration.
- Extended size distribution range (>15 μm).

Observed volume to extinction ratio profiles during the two campaigns.

Presence of super-coarse particles reflected on higher ζ during ASKOS.

Comparing ζ to other methods

 Cyprus
2021-11-15

 Cabo Verde
2022-06-24

Literature

:

AERONET:

WRF:

Agrees within uncertainty

Agrees within uncertainty

Agrees within uncertainty

Big deviations (more than 70%)

Up to 150% differences

Mostly disagree

Scattering calculations of ζ **Cyprus**
 2021-11-15

Better representation by
 particles with low aspect ratios.

 Cabo Verde
 2022-06-24

Not good agreement
 (could improve with the use of
 irregular particles).

Outcomes

- A method for vertically resolved ζ using the combination of UAV-based observations and lidar.
- New experimental observations of ζ , filling gap in literature i.e. EMME region.
- Observational evidence consistent with the presence of transported giant dust particles near desert regions.
- **Publication in ACP (submitted response to the reviewers)**

<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-3404>

Preprint. Discussion started: 29 July 2025

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Volume-to-extinction ratio: An important property of dust

Alkistis Papetta¹, Maria Kezoudi¹, Holger Baars², Athina Floutsi², Eleni Drakaki³, Konrad Kandler⁴, Elena Louca¹, Theodoros Christoudias¹, Eleni Marinou³, Chris Stopford⁵, Troy Thornberry⁶, Vassilis Amiridis³, Jean Sciare¹, and Franco Marengo¹

- Dust optical properties depend on source region and mineralogy.
- Transport over the Mediterranean involves mixing with **pollution** and **sea salt**.

Can optical observations reveal origin and mixing state?

- Identified **four distinct dust events** in the Mediterranean and EMME region.
- Trajectories using HYSPLIT and satellite observations (CALIPSO, IASI).
- Studied optical properties at affected AERONET stations.
- Mineralogical composition simulated by METAL-WRF.

Map of the 4 selected dust events and affected AERONET stations.

Optical properties

- AOD, Ångström exponent (AE), single scattering albedo (SSA), asymmetry factor (ASY) and particle size distribution (PSD) varied significantly between events.

MIDAS dust to aerosol optical depth.

Optical properties

- AOD, Ångström exponent (AE), single scattering albedo (SSA), asymmetry factor (ASY) and particle size distribution (PSD) **varied significantly between events.**

MIDAS dust to aerosol optical depth.

Optical properties

- AOD, Ångström exponent (AE), single scattering albedo (SSA), asymmetry factor (ASY) and particle size distribution (PSD) varied significantly between events.

MIDAS dust to aerosol optical depth.

Aerosol mixing indicators

- PSD: Fine mode dominance
- AE (440-675nm) > 0.8
- SSA < 0.9
- ASY < 0.72

Optical properties

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MIDAS dust to aerosol optical depth.

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MIDAS dust to aerosol optical depth.

Linking optical properties to composition - Case study Middle East Event

METAL-WRF Simulated dust-layer relative concentrations of selected elements during event C.

Linking optical properties to composition - Case study Middle East Event

- Typical dust signature with small variability across stations.
- Iron levels don't explain lower SSA (higher absorption).

METAL-WRF Simulated dust-layer relative concentrations of selected elements during event C.

Linking optical properties to composition - Case study Middle East Event

METAL-WRF Simulated dust-layer relative concentrations of selected elements during event C.

- Typical dust signature with small variability across stations.
- Iron levels don't explain lower SSA (higher absorption).

Average absorption coefficient measured during event C at CAO Agia Marina Xyliatou station.

Linking optical properties to composition - Case study Middle East Event

Agia Marina Xyliatou, Cyprus timeseries

Comparison of UAV-based and ground-based observations of Ca, Al, Fe and Mg with METAL-WRF simulations

Can the measured optical properties of dust reveal its origin and its mixing state with other aerosols during transport?

Outcomes

- Documented the optical and mineralogical variability of major Mediterranean dust outbreaks.
- Identified optical signatures indicative of mixed dust with finer more absorbing aerosols (e.g. pollution)
- Evaluated a mineralogical dust model using UAV-based in-situ observations.
- **Publication in preparation** (collaborative work within the Harmonia COST Action).
- **Next: Radiative effect of dust** during these events (2nd paper in prep, Kouklaki et al.).

Chapter V

Conclusions

Observations of Mineral Dust Using Novel Remote Sensing and UAV Technologies

Q1

How can we improve the reliability of lidar depolarization in the absence of cross-talk parameters?

Q2

How accurate are remote sensing observations of the dust particle size-distribution?

Q3

How are the optical and gravimetric quantifications of dust related?

Q4

Can the measured optical properties of dust reveal its origin and its mixing state with other aerosols during transport?

Q1

How can we ensure that lidar systems accurately distinguish mineral dust from other aerosol types?

Using the **developed methodology** to characterize the depolarization response of lidar systems **using a well-characterized reference lidar** instrument, which was developed and successfully applied as part of this PhD.

Q2

How accurate are remote sensing observations of the dust particle size-distribution?

Partially. UAV-based in-situ observations showed that AERONET retrievals are reliable up to $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$. Still, they showed deviations for super-coarse and giant particles, which can be present during dust events, especially near the source regions.

Q3

How are the optical and gravimetric quantifications of dust related?

Through the **volume-to-extinction ratio (ζ)**, which was for the first time calculated using combined lidar and UAV-based observations. ζ was shown to be underestimated using AERONET, WRF-Chem and literature values in the presence of super-coarse and giant particles.

Q4

Can the measured optical properties of dust reveal its origin and its mixing state with other aerosols during transport?

Yes, the measured optical properties of dust can provide valuable information about its mixing state, particularly when dust interacts with fine anthropogenic aerosols during transport, but they are insufficient on their own to identify dust source regions. Additional mineralogical information from in-situ observations or models is required.

Limitations

- Analysis based on a **limited number of dust events**.
- Current **conclusions** are **region-specific**.
- **UAV observations** are **sparse**, with **limited spatial and temporal coverage**.

Outlook

- Expand volume-to-extinction calculations to additional dust events and regions.
- Exploit UAV-based observations of dust size distribution and mineralogical composition for the improvement of atmospheric models.

19th January, 2026

Alkistis Papetta
PhD VIVA

supported by:

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Thank you for listening

Welcome to the

'Research is what I'm doing when I don't know what I'm doing.'

Extra slides

UAV sensors for dust and other aerosols

SENSOR	UCASS			
USE	Aerosol size distribution 0.4–20 // 3–40 μm	Impactors (>1μm)	Backscatter ratio (2 orientations)	Aerosol size distribution 0.14–3.3 μm

O1: Extra slides

Figure 3.9: Polarization parameters vs time for the second period for the three-parameter approach. The error bars represent the derived parameter's variation within the selected comparison ranges $h_{\delta_m^*}$ and $h_{\delta_{d1,2}}$

O2,3: Extra slides

Date	Campaign	Dust Origin	UAV based				Lidar		Sunphotometer	
			POPS takeoff-landing (UTC)	UCASS takeoff-landing (UTC)	Max climbed alt POPS//UCASS (km ASL)	Dust Layer τ_{eff} (μm)	Dust layer height (km ASL)	VLDR	AOD 500 nm NIC//AMX or OSCM	Ångstrom 447-870 nm
25/10/2021	Fall Campaign, Cyprus	Central Sahara	13:09-14:09	14:24-15:30	3.7//4.0	1.29	2.5-5.2	0.13	0.20//0.16	1.174//1.102
27/10/2021	Fall Campaign, Cyprus	Central Sahara	11:42-12:32	10:48-11:36/13:11-13:59	3.9//4.2/4.0	1.50	2.1-4.4	0.13	0.29//0.28	0.768//0.638
14/11/2021	Fall Campaign, Cyprus	Middle East	13:56-14:39	12:30-13:50/14:42-15:35	3.2//4.4/1.8	1.60	1.4-3.5	0.18	0.28//0.24	0.904//0.816
15/11/2021*	Fall Campaign, Cyprus	Middle East	13:46-14:32	12:37-13:33/14:38-15:36	3.2//4.4/1.5	1.58	1.4-3.4	0.17	0.31//0.25	1.013//0.998
18/11/2021	Fall Campaign, Cyprus	Mixed	13:12-13:58	14:21-15:11	3.8//4.5	1.51	1.4-3.1	0.12	0.37//0.34	1.127//1.104
24/06/2022*	ASKOS, Cabo Verde	West Sahara	15:38-16:51	18:18-19:17	4.9//4.9	3.45	1.6-4.3	0.23	0.47	0.115

02,3: Extra slides

Figure 2. VLDR profiles for 15th November 2021 (a) and 24th June 2022 (b). Vertical lines indicate the timestamps of available PSDs from AERONET (black solid lines), UCASS flight time (box with dashed white line), POPS flight time (box with dotted white line), and the chosen lidar interval (red box).

02,3: Extra slides

Figure 3. Three-hour averaged extinction coefficient, VLDR and PLDR profiles for 15th November 2021 (a) and 24th June 2022 (b). The following reference altitudes (z_{ref}) were used for the Klett inversions: (a), $z_{\text{ref}} = 4$ km a.s.l. and $\text{LR} = 35 \pm 9$ sr; for (b), $z_{\text{ref}} = 5.8$ km a.s.l. and $\text{LR} = 50 \pm 7$ sr. Shaded areas represent the extinction coefficient uncertainty within the chosen time interval. The PLDR is not shown at low extinction ($\leq 10 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$) values due to increased noise levels.

O4: Extra slides

transmission (T_{at}), the reflectance of the underlying surface (R_s), the cloud amount (A_c), the solar constant (S_o), the aerosol optical depth, (τ_{aer}) and the aerosol up scattered fraction, β .

$$dF_{aerosol} = -\frac{1}{2}S_oT_{at}^2(1 - A_c)(1 - R_s)^2\beta_\lambda\tau_{aer\lambda} \quad (3)$$

Technically, S_o , T_{at} and R_s should also be a function of wavelength, λ , but we ignore this here. This expression can only give a negative forcing and hence purely scattering anthropogenic aerosols (i.e. aerosols that appear white as they do not absorb any sunlight) will lead to a negative radiative forcing and hence a cooling of climate. Additionally, this expression suggests that a purely scattering aerosol residing above a dark scene such as a cloud-free ocean surface (low R_s) will give a much stronger cooling than the same aerosol overlying a bright scene such as a snow surface or a cloud (high R_s).

However, most atmospheric aerosols are not purely scattering owing to the presence of absorbing components such as black carbon (soot) and ‘brown’ organic carbon from burning of fossil fuels and biomass, or the presence of absorbing mineral components. This absorption makes aerosol appear grey for industrial and biomass burning aerosols or red/orange/yellow in the case of mineral dust. The parameter that determines the degree of absorption/scattering is known as the aerosol single-scattering albedo, $\omega_{o\lambda}$, defined as:

$$\omega_{o\lambda} = \frac{\sigma_{sca\lambda}}{\sigma_{sca\lambda} + \sigma_{abs\lambda}} \quad (4)$$

where σ_{sca} and σ_{abs} are the scattering and absorption efficiencies that are frequently computed for a distribution of aerosols using the scattering theory of Mie [13]. An aerosol single-scattering albedo of 1 indicates a purely scattering (white) aerosol. Aerosols such as industrial pollution typically exhibit $\omega_{0.55\mu m}$ of around 0.85–0.97 [11] while biomass burning aerosols can exhibit $\omega_{0.55\mu m}$ in the region 0.75–0.95 [14], depending on the intensity of the combustion, which determines the ratio of absorbing black carbon to less absorbing organic carbon. A simple expression for the forcing from a partially absorbing aerosol can be formulated [15]:

$$dF \approx -\frac{1}{2}S_oT_{at}^2(1 - A_c) \left[(1 - R_s)^2 - \frac{2R_s}{\beta} \left(\frac{1}{\omega_o} - 1 \right) \right] \omega_o\beta\tau_{aer}$$